

e- ISSN: 3048-6068

Volume 08 Issue 02
May-Aug 2026

*Corresponding Author:
Aryan Manhas,
*Department of Computer
Science & Engineering,
RV Institute of
Technology and
Management, Bengaluru*

Edge and Cloud Computing: A Survey of Architectures, Challenges, and Opportunities

Aryan Manhas¹, Gajanan M Naik²

¹*Student, Department of Computer Science & Engineering,
RV Institute of Technology and Management, Bengaluru*

²*Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical
Engineering, RV Institute of Technology and
Management, Bengaluru*

ABSTRACT

The popularity of IoT devices these days demands low-latency applications have exposed the limitations of traditional Cloud Computing. Edge paradigm has emerged with a different approach, by bringing computation & storage nearer to the sources of data. This paper provides a survey on Edge-Cloud computing by focusing on its architecture models, challenges faced in adopting the said models and future opportunities. Finally, we explore the promising future of this system as well as its implementation in the synergy with AI/ML and impact on 5G/6G networks. This survey serves as a valuable lesson for understanding the present state and future evolution of Edge & Cloud Computing.

Keywords:-*Edge Computing, Cloud Computing, Edge-Cloud Architecture, Internet of Things (IoT), Survey*

1. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing can be defined as a technology that allows users to store, manage, and process data on data (remote) centers instead of on their local computers. Multiple companies provide this service such as Amazon (AWS), Google (GCP), or Microsoft (Azure) to name a few. Cloud Computing has established itself as a cornerstone of modern digital infrastructure, offering unprecedented scalability, on-demand resources, and centralized data processing power. But nowadays IoT is being used in every sector of our lives such as vehicles to Augmented Reality (AR), due to this specific needs such as ultra-low latency, real-time decision-making, and efficient use of network bandwidth have become necessary and which were not fulfilled due to physical distance of remote cloud data centers.

To solve the issue present in cloud computing, edge computing has emerged. What edge computing does is that it brings data processing closer to the source of data - like IoT devices, sensors, or smartphones - rather than relying on distant cloud servers which further reduces the latency and are important for mission - critical services. However the true strength is not in replacing cloud computing with edge but creating a symbiotic cloud - edge system that leverages the strength of both such as the responsiveness and context-awareness of the edge with the robust computational and storage capabilities of the cloud. Cloud - Edge system sounds revolutionary in planning but its possibility for implementation still remains a mystery. This paper presents a comprehensive survey of the Edge-Cloud computing paradigm. We provide 3 major contributions. First we provide a systematic taxonomy of Edge-Cloud architectures, classifying existing models to bring more clarity for pros and cons for each model. Second, we conduct an

analysis of the major issues that impede the global implementation of these systems. Finally, we will discuss future possible implementation of this system in technologies like 5G/6G networks and Artificial Intelligence (AI). This survey aims to serve as a foundation and the future roadmap for this everchanging field.

2. LITERATURE SELECTION PROCESS

To ensure that the quality of this paper is maintained and to follow the systematic review of this field, this survey has gone through a very strict literature selection process. Prominent academic databases, such as IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, and Google Scholar were further reviewed so that the paper follows the original key structure mentioned above. The search queries used keywords related to the paper's main themes, such as "Edge and Cloud Computing", "Edge-Cloud architectures", "Edge AI" and "Edge security".

Our literature selection process made sure that all the information was published between the years 2018 and 2025 so that it covers the latest and relevant advancements. We also excluded patents, technical reports, and non-English publications. The initial search yielded hundreds of papers that were further reviewed and refined so that they were related to our topics.

3. DISCUSSION

A. Architecture: In this section we will discuss about the working architecture and service models present for both Cloud and Edge Computing:

- a) **Cloud Computing:** In cloud computing, resources are shared through infrastructure. Cloud provides an extra level of abstraction between the resources and the elements like storage, network and service. The service providers

provide services in majorly 3 types. These 3 types are Platform-as-a-Services (PaaS), Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS), and Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) [1].

- Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) : Service provided by PaaS to the user is gone through the Internet. The major advantage of PaaS is that the user

doesn't need to install the software or require hardware, which therefore saves cost. PaaS has built-in tools & security and also includes interfaces for the web applications [1].

Examples:

- a) Business Intelligence
- b) Database
- c) Development and testing

- Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) : IaaS provides users with a machine that has an already installed and configured operating system as per the user's needs. The data is stored in servers present in different locations all over the world. Users access services like the storage, network infra and computing resources. Service providers only help the user with the software and hardware, which includes services like servers and storage devices [1].

Examples:

- a. Content Delivery Networks: It records & delivers content & other resources to improve the system performance.
- b. Backup and Recovery: This helps in backup & restoration of folders and files during a data loss.
- c. Storage: Storage ability to store important applications, files and their backups for recovery.

- **Software-as-a-Service (SaaS):** In SaaS, both the group of software and infrastructure provided to the user is owned by the service provider.

Examples are applications that can be accessed simultaneously by various consumers from anywhere in the internet [1].

Examples:

- Applications:** Email, word editors, spreadsheets, are the typical examples.
- Billing:** Applications are designed so that billing of the customer is managed.
- Financials:** Applications used for managing financial information such as expenditure, payroll and taxes.

B. Edge Computing: The growth of internet and IoT resulted in serious problems for the centralized cloud computing architectures. Mobile devices connected with a centralized cloud server have been used in difficult and complex applications, giving rise to additional burden on the radio access network. In this case, edge computing provides storage and computing resources as well as serving as a new layer, with edge devices between the IoT devices and the cloud computing layer. Technology to solve the above mentioned problems of cloud:

a) **Cloudlet:** Known as micro cloud data centers, it operates similarly to the small cloud computing architecture. Cloudlets are used to serve time-critical applications under less resourceful conditions. The difference of cost between traditional cloud and cloudlet is justified due to how important the role is in where cloudlet is used. Cloudlets are mostly used in mobile applications with massive resource requirements and provide it while decreasing latency. Results show that up to 51% - 42% reduction in the response time while using cloudlets instead of clouds[2].

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF CLOUD COMPUTING AND CLOUDLET

Characteristics	Cloud	Cloudlet
Computing power	High	Moderate
Resource flexibility	High	High
User acceptance	Acceptable QoE	Excellent QoE
Accessibility	High	High
Client mobility	High	Limited
Cost	High	Low-free
Latency	High	Low
Data security	High	Intermittent
Management	Centralized – complicated	Non-centralized – self-managed
Offline availability	Unavailable	Available
Bandwidth	Low	High
Storage capacity	Pay-as-you-go	High
WAN requirement	Persistent connection	None
State	Hard & soft state	Soft state
Network resource allocation	Large of users (1000s)	A few users (10s)
Deployment environment	Large data centers, controlled environments	Capable virtual deployment at any place
Disaster impact	Catastrophic	Lowest influence

b) Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) in IoT:

MEC gives the chance of computation at edge. MEC is present in the mobile network base station and sometimes is

called Mobile Cloud Computing (MCC). In MCC structure, data storage, data processing is done outside the mobile device. MEC made it possible to lessen the process duration and energy required

by devices through the deploying computing resources, network controlling in the vicinity of Cell Base Stations. MEC and MCC systems are quite different regarding computing server,

end-user distance, and latency. MEC is significantly better than MCC due to its lesser latency and better energy efficiency in mobile devices and better secured privacy [2].

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF MEC AND MCC SYSTEM

	MEC	MCC
Server hardware	Small-scaled data centers possessing moderate resources	Large-scaled data centers (containing numerous high-capability servers)
Server location	Co-located along with wireless gateways, WiFi routers, and LTE BSs	Installed at especial buildings as big as several football fields
Deployment	Heavily exploited by telecom operators, MEC vendors, enterprises, and home users. Requiring light configurations and planning	Used by IT companies, such as Google and Amazon, at a limited number of sites around the globe. Requiring complicated configurations and planning
Distance to end users	Short (tens to hundreds of meters)	Long (sometimes across-continental)
Backhaul usage	Infrequent use improve congestion	Frequent application probable congestion
System management	Hierarchical (centralized/dispersed)	Centralized
Supportable latency	Below 10 ms	Over 100 ms
Applications	Latency-critical and computation-intensive tasks, such as AR, automatic driving, and interactive online games	Latency-tolerant and computation-intensive application, such as online social networking and mobile commerce/health/learning

c) Fog computing:

Fog computing can be defined as a system-level architecture capable of distributing computation resources, storage and control to nearby users. The main purpose is to act as a bridge between cloud service and devices. The main reason why the cloud is shifted

towards the edge is to make resources present at the cloud to be available at edge. Fog computing is just a significantly improved and expanded deployment version of cloud. It also improves the drawbacks that come with conventional cloud computing[2].

TABLE III. ADVANTAGES AND DRAWBACKS OF FOG COMPUTING

Pros	Cons
System response time improvement	Trust and authentication anxiety
System response time improvement	Wan security concerns
Systematic mobility support	Security issues such as man in the middle and IP address bluffing
Minimization of the core network latency	Accessibility or cost of fog facilities/hardware
Superfluous data restriction support to send at cloud	The physical location could be stolen from any data benefit of the cloud regardless of time and place
Security enhancement by keeping data close to the edge	Privacy issues as a result of the distributed processing schemes

C. Challenges: Both Cloud and Edge computing have many issues related to them. The following section talks about that. The major challenges can be divided into section:

4. SECURITY AND PRIVACY

The biggest challenge is how to address security and privacy issues which occur during the movement of data on the network, loss of control on data, and many other security problems. The storage, processing and movement of data outside the system of control comes with its own inherent risks which makes it vulnerable to cyber-attacks. It also comes with huge privacy concerns because service providers have access to data that can be changed, compromised or even removed without the knowledge of the user[4].

• **Performance**

Performance is also a huge issue that comes into play with cloud computing. The cloud provider needs to give the user high performance when they switch to cloud infrastructure. The applications with intensive demand can be more challenging to provide high quality performance for the cloud provider. Which might lead to poor performance which further leads to user dissatisfaction and results in loss of customers, end of service delivery and

reduced revenues[4].

• **Reliability and Availability**

Reliability is the most important quality for the modern day demand from the users. Which causes major issues as when the cloud is down the reliability of that cloud service provider is first to take a hit. Availability is as important as reliability in the modern day and age. Regardless of how much a cloud service provider promises on reliability and availability, the cloud service can easily experience DoS (Denial of Service) attacks, performance cuts, equipment outages, power cuts and natural disasters[4].

These are some of the major concerns and challenges that come with cloud computing. Now we will discuss problems faced with the edge computing paradigm. Similarly to the cloud computing the challenges faced in edge computing are classified into 3 major groups:

• **Resource Management**

Edge computing system is based on transfer of resources from the cloud to the nearest end node. IoT devices where edge computing is most widely used has very high resource constraints, which is a huge challenge. There are many recent inventions focused on solving this issue [3].

- **Security and Privacy**

In recent times there is steady increase by users in adoption of fog and edge computing. Which itself comes with many advantages but there are still some major drawbacks which need solving. One of them is surely privacy & security issues. This is also one of the reasons which slows the progress of the edge and fog computing itself [3].

- **Network Management**

Most important technologies which facilitate both fog and edge computing is network management as it helps with the connection between all smart devices at the edge. And also it provides all the edge devices with resources. The IoT network includes different types of devices with varying connectivity and maintenance of different levels of significance is also at some level handled by it [3].

Opportunities: The future of both edge and cloud computing will be shaped by various technological advancements and innovations. Some of the key developments expected to impact these domains include:

- Federated Learning and Distributed AI
- Quantum Computing
- 5G/6G Networks
- Edge Data Centers
- Serverless Computing
- Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)

These technological advancements and innovations are expected to shape the future of edge and cloud computing, driving new opportunities and use cases across various industries. As these technologies continue to evolve and mature, organizations will be able to leverage the benefits of both edge and cloud computing to address complex challenges and enable digital

transformation [5].

5. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a survey on the Edge-Cloud limitations as well how it is used presently and the future of it. This review was structured around the three core pillars of this domain: architectures, challenges, and opportunities.

This survey starts with the present service models of Cloud Computing—IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS which are explained briefly as well as their use case in the industry. We also analyzed the key emerging edge paradigms, identifying Cloudlets, Mobile Edge Computing and Fog Computing.

Then we analyse the challenges that will be faced by both cloud and edge computing paradigm.

For the cloud, these are primarily concerns of security, performance, and reliability. The edge

faces the issue of resource management, network management, and its own unique security and privacy issues.

Finally, we review the future of the Edge-Cloud. And it includes Distributed AI and Federated Learning, and the ultra-low-latency networks enabled by 5G and 6G.

This paper shows that integration of edge and cloud is a necessary evolution. This survey serves as a foundational roadmap for understanding the current state and future potential of this ever-changing field.

REFERENCES

1. Odun-Ayo, M. Ananya, F. Agono and R. Goddy-Worlu, "Cloud Computing Architecture: A Critical Analysis," 2018 18th International Conference on Computational Science and Applications (ICCSA), Melbourne, VIC, Australia, 2018
2. Hamdan, S.; Ayyash, M.; Almajali, S. Edge-Computing Architectures for Internet of Things Applications: A Survey. Sensors 2020
3. M. Talebkhah, A. Sali, M. Marjani, M.

- Gordan, S. J. Hashim and F. Z. Rokhani, "Edge computing: Architecture, Applications and Future Perspectives," 2020 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Engineering and Technology (IICAIET), Kota Kinabalu, Malaysia, 2020
4. Sajid, Mohammad, and Zahid Raza. "Cloud computing: Issues & challenges." International conference on cloud, big data and trust. Vol. 20. No. 13. sn, 2013.
 5. Bajic, Bojana, et al. "EDGE COMPUTING VS. CLOUD COMPUTING: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN INDUSTRY 4.0." Annals of DAAAM & Proceedings 30 (2019).